

JENGA: PRACTISING SELF-EFFICACY, ONE BLOCK AT A TIME by Iniobong Udo (MSc, MPH, PMP)

Innovation in Public health does not always require high-tech tools neither does it always require large scale interventions. Sometimes, simple, interactive activities could drive home key relatable messages helping individuals internalise complex concepts thereby building skills needed to improve health outcome.

As a public health professional with years of experience working in the community whether addressing concerns about substance misuse or having conversations around period poverty, I have found that using simple approach leaves a lasting impression that could bring about mindset reorientation from individuals who may be marginalised or vulnerable.

Recently while facilitating a group on building self –efficacy for individuals in recovery from alcohol and substance misuse, I have employed the Jenga games. In Jenga games, each block represents a small but meaningful step which could be healthy habit, a personal strength or a coping strategy in

recovery. As participants carefully build the tower, they reflect on what solid foundation they have put in place to support their recovery. As the tower rises, participants see how every piece (decision) matters. While adjusting the tower as it rises, reflection focuses on what life adjustments is made in order to prevent relapse. On the other hand, a wobbly tower shows that immediate fear/doubt that often creeps in while in recovery – doubts about going off-track and possible relapse. In any event the platform upon which Jenga is built shakes and the tower collapses, reflection is focused on what external factors may have caused a relapse. However, such sudden lapse/relapse does not affect the base (foundation) hence the importance of having a solid foundation. While rebuilding the tower, the process may become easier as the base is a proof of existing experience, showing skills that was cultivated at the first attempt to build the Jenga tower. On successful completion of the tower, the traditional Jenga game begins where each piece of block is strategically removed, one piece at a time. Each piece that is removed and restacked, represents both risk and control. This enhances the participant's ability to learn decision making under pressure in a safe environment.

The game summarises self-efficacy which is the ability to successfully carry out a specific task/behaviour. Self-efficacy in recovery is crucial; individuals who believe they can manage triggers, high-risk situations, attend therapeutic sessions, develop and maintain routines are most likely to follow through with healthy behaviours.

Through Jenga, participants practice planning, patience and rebuilding with the realisation that mistakes/slips do not equal failure – they can try again and succeed as a bend does not necessarily mean an end. This mirrors real-world recovery: each small success reinforces their ability to maintain long term behavioural change which is core public health goal in substance misuse interventions.

When self-efficacy is targeted rather than general confidence, a simple game like Jenga becomes tangible public health tool, promoting resilience, problem solving, critical thinking, and sustainable engagement in recovery.